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The role of drone technologies in forest fire management

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Wildfires represent a significant natural hazard causing economic losses, deaths, and environmental damage and although systems are used for remote detection and monitoring, they only provide good performance in the area of efficient data collection and fire characterization in small-scale environments. However, when wildfires are large-scale, some of these ground-based systems are not suitable for optimal coverage. To address this limitation, unmanned aerial vehicles (drones) and associated technologies are starting to be used, which can provide an efficient and low-cost alternative for prevention, detection, and real-time support of wildfire suppression. This review chapter presents and analyzes the contribution of UAV/drone technologies in wildfire management.

Keywords: Drone technologies, Forest fires, Environmental damage, Natural hazard.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The frequency and level of incidence or impact of natural disasters are increasing worldwide [1]. The size and scale of the disaster make it very difficult for people to respond and address the crisis immediately; in some situations, it is almost impossible for people to react in time to the catastrophe [2]. Attempts are currently being made to anticipate and foresee the possible occurrence of a disaster to effectively respond to a crisis amid a tragedy, quickly and accurately assess the impact, remedy and restore normal conditions [3]. In this line, forest fires are a major threat in forested, rural, and protected areas. Their control and mitigation are difficult as they can spread rapidly to their surroundings, potentially burning large areas of land and approaching urban areas and cities. The occurrence of forest fires generates substantial costs for the economy, ecosystems, and climate [4].

Since wildfires are a multifaceted problem, many different elements are relevant to efforts to reduce their impact. Aspects such as meteorology, drought monitoring, and vegetation status monitoring can help in prevention and preparedness for wildfires. Other aspects such as fire suppression actions and post-fire recovery strategies after the outbreak of a fire must also be taken into account. When it comes to managing the mitigation of an ongoing wildfire, emergency managers already use technologies associated with unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) as support. Aerial Vehicle UAVs, commonly known as drones (in this work both terms will be used interchangeably) [5-8].

UAV technologies have seen a major advancement in the last decade and are now used in a wide range of civilian applications. UAVs have become smaller, and more affordable, and now have better computing capabilities than in the past, making them reliable tools for remote sensing missions in harsh environments [9]. Furthermore, UAVs can fly or hover (static positioning in flight) over specific areas to retrieve relevant data in real time with cameras or other sensors. As a result, real-world research, studies, and experience have demonstrated their benefits for wildfire surveillance and monitoring, as well as for tasks related to post-fire damage assessment [9-12]. Furthermore, UAVs have shown a positive economic balance in favor of their use in wildfire emergencies [13, 14].

This review chapter presents and analyses the functionalities and performance of drone technologies in the context of forest fires. Research in this area predominantly revolves around fire detection and monitoring, so the core of this review will focus on the technologies and approaches intended to address these activities. The rest of the document has the following structure: the next section presents the methodological approach adopted; then the conceptual framework is developed; in the penultimate section, and at the resulting level, the main core of the work is developed; and finally, in the last section of the chapter, the appropriate conclusions are formulated.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) /drones

UAVs can be classified into fixed-wing, rotary-wing, and hybrid fixed/rotary-wing based on their design, range, size, weight, flight mechanisms, and power source [20, 21]. A fixed-wing UAV can fly at high altitudes and can quickly survey a wide area, while rotary UAVs, which are very small in size, can hover (stationary) at low altitudes and collect high-resolution data [22].

UAV structures are generally simpler than those of rotary-wing UAVs, so they require less complicated maintenance and repair processes and can therefore operate for longer periods and at higher speeds [23]. In addition, they can carry large payloads over farther distances using less energy, as they have natural gliding capabilities without the need for power, but these vehicles require a runway or similar infrastructure to take off and land [23].

Rotary-wing (multirotor) UAVs depending on the number of rotors are called: tricopters, quadcopters, hexacopters, octocopters, and coaxial. These UAVs can land and take off vertically, which is why they are known as Vertical Take-Off and Landing vehicles VTOL, and this makes them suitable to act in any type of

situation and topography [24] [5]. A hybrid drone is a UAV that combines the advantages of fixed-wing and rotary-wing UAVs [25]. In short, all three types of UAVs: fixed-wing, rotary-wing, and hybrid unmanned aerial vehicles are effectively used in different forest fire management operations.

Early detection of wildfires has been used with both fixed-wing and rotary-wing drones equipped with optical or thermal cameras [25]. UAVs can be deployed in different numbers and scenarios depending on the frequency and severity of wildfires in a region.

2.2 Natural Disaster Management

Disasters, both natural and man-made, are generally unpredictable events that negatively impact people's lives, the economy, and development. Therefore, it is necessary to learn about the nature of disasters, their phases, and components (prediction, preparation, occurrence or development, response, and recovery) to be able to react to various types of natural and man-made catastrophes and develop viable methods and techniques for managing such disasters [26].

To deal with various forms of natural disasters and create viable disaster management procedures and approaches, it is crucial to understand what type of disaster it is its components, and its phases. This section explains the typical stages of a disaster management system. Pre-disaster (i.e. before the outbreak of the disaster), during the development of the disaster, and post-disaster (this is the longest and most complex stage since what is managed here are the consequences generated by the disaster) are the three stages that make up the disaster process or life cycle [27]. Throughout the pre-disaster stage, UAVs are used to prepare and identify regions that are vulnerable to disasters to establish effective measures to lessen the negative effects of both natural and man-made disasters.

This allows UAVs to collect the necessary data from authorities to establish the necessary preparedness and prevention steps before the disaster breaks out. The following period refers to the onset or outbreak of the disaster and lasts until it stops; the times depend on the typology of the disaster, which may be short or long-term. Short-term disasters would be, for example, tremors or earthquakes, landslides/avalanches (on mountain slopes) lasting a few seconds, tornadoes (lasting several minutes or a few hours), and forest fires (small and punctual) that can last a few hours. On the other hand, a long-term disaster, such as tsunamis, floods, hurricanes, large forest fires, erupting volcanoes, etc., occurs over longer periods and can last up to several days. At this stage of the disaster, usually very destructive, UAV systems are used to monitor the progression of the catastrophe [28].

Using such monitoring, officials can measure the magnitude/size of the disaster in real-time to determine the most affected areas and thus allocate resources to improve relief operations. Over time, UAVs can be very useful for post-disaster assessment and infrastructure damage assessment, actions that take place during the third stage after a disaster. Data obtained from UAVs during this last stage can be important for the emergency management team, humanitarian organizations, and government agencies. In the third stage, UAVs can be used in search and rescue activities as well as in rehabilitation monitoring [29-31].

2.2.1 Forest Fire Management

In the context of the present research, forest fire emergency management, two factors are presented as the most relevant. First, the lapse between the start of a fire and the arrival of firefighters and rescuers; this response time must be reduced to a minimum to decrease the chances of the fire spreading to unmanageable levels. The second key factor is the assessment of the magnitude of the event and the monitoring of the emergency response [32, 33]. Since the manual assessment of forest fires is hampered by several factors, consideration of this aspect is necessary to develop better firefighting strategies.

These key factors can only be adequately addressed by developing reliable and efficient systems for early-stage fire detection and monitoring. In this line, remote sensing has been widely used as it allows observation (using satellite images) of forest fires without unnecessarily exposing humans to dangerous activities [34-36]. Wireless sensor networks (WSNs) have also been proposed for forest fire detection, monitoring, and

assessment [22, 37, 38]. However, both types of systems have practical limitations. Satellite images have limited resolution, which makes it difficult to detect small fires [39]. In addition, satellites have limited land coverage and need a significant amount of time before they can rescan the same region.

Limited accuracy and lack of real-time data reporting therefore make satellite imagery unsuitable for continuous monitoring. As for wireless sensor networks, they function as an infrastructure that must be deployed in advance. Since sensors are installed in the forest, their coverage and resolution are proportional to the investment made in their acquisition and deployment. Furthermore, in the event of a fire, sensors are destroyed, resulting in additional replacement costs.

Maintenance difficulties, lack of energy independence and the fact that they are not scalable due to their static nature are factors that limit their coverage and effectiveness [40]. As a result of the shortcomings of previous systems, in recent years unmanned aerial vehicles/drones are being used as a more convenient technology for this task. Their maneuverability, autonomy, easy deployment, and relatively low cost are attributes that made UAVs the technology of choice to support forest fire management.

3. METHOD

For the present review work, a typical methodology in this type of research called *systematic mapping was used*, which is the process of identifying, categorizing, and analyzing the existing literature that is relevant to a certain research topic [15-19]. The objective of this review is to show an overview of the related scientific field, in this case, that of the functionality of drones and their associated technologies in emergency management due to a forest fire. This systematic mapping is developed in three basic blocks: 1) definition for the search, where the research question, the scope of the review, the inclusion and exclusion criteria, and finally the search string are defined; 2) execution of the search; and 3) presentation and analysis of the results.

Regarding the definition of the search, the research questions are those related to the foundations of the dual concept of *UAV / forest fire management*, namely: why are UAVs necessary in forest fire management? And what are and how do UAV or drone technologies contribute to forest fire management? Regarding the scope of the review, a search was carried out in the following digital catalogs: ScienceDirect, IEEE Xplore, Taylor & Francis, Springer, Wiley, SAGE, and JSTOR. The following descriptors were used for the search: *drone, unmanned aerial vehicle, remotely piloted aerial vehicle, drone technology, natural disaster, emergency management, disaster management, wildfire, search and rescue*. The search period was 2005-2024.

The following inclusion/exclusion criteria were applied to filter the studies: 1) all scientific publications that are only related to the field of study or ongoing research were included; 2) studies published in English and Spanish were included; 3) case studies were included, as long as they provided a related conceptual framework and concrete, measurable and comparable results; 4) articles without a research design and a well-defined research question were excluded; 5) tertiary reviews were excluded; 6) thematic review papers were excluded; 7) papers on opinion polls or similar were excluded; 8) technical reports or studies without a solid scientific basis were excluded; and 9) all *grey literature* that did not present a solid, rigorous and formal theoretical foundation was excluded. Finally, regarding the search conduct, two review filters were applied: 1) first review filter: title of the article, abstract, and keywords; and 2) second review filter: full text of the article.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Drone assistance tasks in forest fire management

Remote sensing with aerial systems presents multiple advantages in the context of emergency assistance for natural disasters. Their high maneuverability allows them to dynamically survey a region, follow a defined path, or navigate autonomously. The wide range of sensors that can be carried on board allows for capturing important data that can be used to monitor the situation of interest and plan an emergency response. The ability to remotely control UAVs helps reduce the risk for disaster mitigation teams and first responders. Automation of maneuvers, planning, and other mission-related tasks through a computer

interface improves remote surveillance and monitoring. Advances in these aspects have a direct impact on the management of resources against forest fires [41, 42].

UAV forest fire assistance systems can be characterized using four attributes [43]: detection modalities and instruments, type of task performed, coordination strategies (with multiple UAVs) with the emergency control center, and the approach to experimental validation. Fire detection and monitoring is based on reconnaissance techniques, a field of research that has seen significant advances in recent years. Meanwhile, forecasting (the existence of a forest fire) has practical limitations that make its implementation difficult.

Forecasting requires complex mathematical models that must be fed with data that can be difficult to acquire in real time and unknown environments. Firefighting, on the other hand, requires expensive firefighting equipment, which is even more costly in the case of large wildfires. In addition, proximity to fires can pose a significant risk to the integrity of the aerial vehicle and lead to its loss. However, some initial research has been done to design a UAV capable of fighting fires [44-46].

A key component of an airborne fire support system is the type of UAV used. UAVs have different sizes, maneuverability, and endurance capabilities. These characteristics in themselves have a strong influence on the overall system architecture. There is a wide selection of airborne systems ranging from large UAVs with high endurance and high processing capabilities to small UAVs with short flight times and limited processing capabilities. Large vehicles are very expensive, but have a larger payload capacity and can carry more sensors and other relevant instruments. On the other hand, smaller vehicles are economically more affordable, but with limited payload capacity.

Onboard instruments vary between the systems analyzed, but some are essential for navigation and localization and are therefore found in almost all UAVs. The Global Navigation Satellite System GNSS and the Inertial Navigation System INS fall into the latter category. Furthermore, almost all vehicles analyzed have at least one type of imaging sensor used for different purposes, including fire detection. Temperature sensors are also present in some of the proposed fire assistance systems [47]. Measurements from the sensors are the inputs to fire detection algorithms that process the data to detect the existence of fires. The processing can be done on board the UAV or by a computer located at the emergency management center.

The coordination strategy, in emergency management, provides the framework for the deployment of flight missions. Surveillance missions are usually planned and aim to search wide areas, prioritizing areas with the highest risk of fire. These missions can be performed by humans manually operating the UAVs. The coordination strategy itself becomes more critical during the monitoring of the spread of a fire, as the flight plan needs to be adapted to the spread of the fire. This is even more relevant if multiple UAVs are collaborating on the mission during a wildfire emergency [32]. For example, a UAV could hover (static hover) near a fire site and alert the rest of the fleet to proceed with fire confirmation [48]. More complex planning is also possible, requiring consensus on the task to be performed by each unit or flying in a specific formation around the fire perimeter [20, 49]. In both cases, a concrete task description and autonomous decision scheme must be defined for the system to be effective.

4.2 Support technologies installed in drones

Sensors provide the data needed for navigation for monitoring and assistance in the event of a forest fire. In outdoor scenarios, GNSS and INS provide the real-time location of the UAV. They are also used to georeference the captured images, thus allowing geographic mapping of fires. Fires have specific signatures that can be composed of different elements such as heat, movement, brightness, smoke, and generation of bioproducts. These elements can be measured using suitable sensors installed on drones. Cameras are the detection instruments that offer the greatest versatility in their measurement. Visual and infrared sensors on board UAVs can be used to capture a large amount of information [50].

In another order, visible spectrum cameras are widely available and commonly used in various applications. They come in a wide variety of resolutions, form factors, and costs. Their versatility offers a valuable

alternative in forest fire investigation from both a technical and commercial perspective. Furthermore, the constant reduction in size and weight of visible cameras makes them perfect candidates for UAVs. The data provided by these sensors are grayscale images or RGB (red, green, and blue) format [51, 52]. This allows the development of computer vision techniques using color, shape, temporal changes, and motion in images or a sequence of images. Although versatile and widely available, visible light sensors must be carefully selected for night operations, as some sensors perform poorly in low-light conditions. Despite some of their limitations, they equip almost all UAVs and make them good candidates for forest fire detection and monitoring [53-56].

On the other hand, multispectral cameras are available. The use of each spectral band alone has its limitations, so the use of multiple cameras and combining multiple spectra is proposed. This allows the use of data fusion techniques to increase the accuracy of fire detection in complex situations and under different lighting conditions [10, 57]. Other alternatives combine small sensors, such as visible spectrum sensors and infrared sensors [48].

Finally, the use of various sensors other than cameras to detect and confirm the presence of wildfires has also been proposed. Some research proposes the use of chemical sensors that can detect concentrations of hazardous compounds [58]. Spectrometry measurements are another approach that can be used to detect characteristics of burned vegetation and confirm a fire [50]. Temperature sensors have been used in some situations to generate heat maps and detect/locate fires [59]; on the other hand, the use of temperature sensors to estimate fire contour and rate of spread is proposed in the context of fire modeling [59-61]. While interesting, these sensors are limited compared to infrared cameras that can provide more comprehensive data.

4.3 Forest fire detection and segmentation

Real-life experiences have demonstrated the effectiveness of UAVs as a remote sensing tool in forest firefighting scenarios [10, 58, 62]. They are very useful even in simple tasks such as observing the fire from a static (aerial) position and transmitting the video sequence to emergency managers (either at the fire site or to the emergency management center). This simple use case already allows firefighters to have an aerial view of the spreading fire and to plan containment measures. However, a single drone, piloted remotely (at or near the scene of the incident), although very useful for small fires, is not suitable for large wildfires. Therefore, automation of fire detection and monitoring can help to provide optimal coverage of the fire area with the help of multiple UAVs and with less human intervention. In addition, the collected data can be further processed to analyze the fire, estimate its rate of spread, and volume, or perform post-fire damage assessment [10, 63].

To perform fire-related tasks autonomously, systems need to address different subtasks such as fire geolocation, fire modeling, and even route planning and coordination between UAVs. For this purpose, sensor data is often initially processed to detect a wildfire and take mitigation measures. For fire detection, existing systems can usually directly extract fire-like pixels based on color signals or infrared intensities and do not require additional analysis. However, monitoring tasks often require additional analysis to estimate the fire perimeter or burned areas. In that context, the computed measures (e.g., segmentation) are provided as input to fire models to estimate the fire spread over time [64].

Fire segmentation is the process of extracting pixels corresponding to fire in an image. The criteria by which a pixel is selected vary from method to method. The selection criteria are also the main factor affecting the detection accuracy. In general, fire segmentation uses the pixel values of an image from the visual spectrum (e.g., color space segmentation) or the intensities of an infrared image. Motion segmentation can also be used to extract fire using its motion over a sequence of images [65, 66]. In recent years, deep learning algorithms have shown excellent results in different areas. Regarding UAVs, previous works using deep convolutional neural networks mainly dealt with fire detection [56, 67, 68].

On the other hand, fire segmentation using static images helps to reduce the search space, but objects with similar color to the fire can often be detected and lead to false positives. Some research proposes the use

of an optical flow algorithm to consider fire motions [69]. By detecting corresponding feature points in consecutive image frames, a relative motion vector can be calculated. The mean motion vector matches the motion of the UAV, except for moving objects on the ground. Fire flames are located among such objects due to their random motion. By detecting feature points within regions with random motion and similar colors to the fire, the fire can be confirmed and the false alarm rate can be reduced [52, 55].

In another order, the data that feeds a fire detection system is analyzed to find patterns that confirm the occurrence of the event. Patterns are recognized by calculating different features that can be strong or weak signatures for a specific application. In the case of fire detection with unmanned aerial vehicles, the most popular features are color, brightness, and motion. Research focused on fire detection considers the fusion of more features to obtain better results in the classification stage. These features can be classified according to the level of abstraction at which they are extracted: pixel, spatial, and temporal [65, 70].

Additional features can improve wildfire detection. Features obtained through temporal analysis evaluate the difference between adjacent frames. In simple scenarios, where the camera is static and the background is not complex, frame subtractions can help detect moving pixels. In the presence of complex and dynamic backgrounds, Gaussian mixture models and other sophisticated background modeling techniques can be considered [71].

However, video streams from UAVs have fast motions and no classical background subtraction method would give satisfactory results due to the assumption of a static camera. Even in a situation where the UAV is hovering over a fixed position, images are still affected by wind turbulence and vibrations. Therefore, to be able to apply these motion analysis techniques, image alignment, and video stabilization need to be considered. The usual approach is to find strong feature points that can be tracked in a sequence of frames [72, 73].

4.4 Data management and processing

A large number of wildfire detection approaches use a classification method that is based on learning algorithms. The main challenge of machine learning is to build or find a sufficiently large dataset with low bias. Such a dataset should contain positive examples with high feature variance and negative examples consisting of standard samples.

Deep learning techniques require even larger data sets for training. Data augmentation techniques can help in this regard, but they require a sufficiently large data set to start with. In the case of forest fire detection, a sufficiently large usable data set is not yet available, which could be problematic for the development of a fire detection module for forest fire assistance systems; and fire samples in video format are also necessary for the development of UAV-based systems. However, some practical experiences or applications are already being carried out that can help UAVs improve the development of the algorithms needed in a forest fire assistance system [74, 75].

4.5 Geolocation of forest fires and their modeling

In a forest fire scenario, when a fire is detected, the UAV must alert the emergency management center and send the geolocation of the fire to deploy the extinguishing means. The reviewed literature identifies two different levels of approach for the detection alert. Some research uses a local approach in which the position of the fire is reported at first contact, while other studies go further by addressing the problem globally by identifying and locating the entire perimeter of the fire.

The simplest alerting approach is to directly provide the geographic coordinates of the UAV using the onboard GPS when a fire is first detected. This can be performed with good accuracy when the UAV is flying at low altitudes and has its data acquisition sensor pointing at the ground at a 90° angle, thus localizing critical points of the fire [59]. A similar approach is possible with a camera located at the bottom of a UAV and facing downwards. However, for a camera located at the front of the UAV, it is necessary to calculate a projection of the camera plane onto a global coordinate system using homography.

UAV pose estimation is reliable when the terrain is mostly flat. Some difficulties arise in the presence of irregular surfaces. Some techniques overcome this limitation by exploiting a previously known digital elevation map of the studied area, this map allows us to estimate the location from where the fire originated and therefore improves the estimation of the fire location. To reduce errors, a fleet of UAVs observing the same hotspot can be used, first to detect the fire and then using different views of the UAVs to refine the estimates [10, 48, 72, 76].

To better characterize ongoing wildfires, some researchers have studied fire models to provide global information such as fire boundaries and behavior. The simplest models use an elliptical shape that is adapted to the fire and where each ellipse axis increases at a given rate. Here, the rate at which the ellipse axis grows depends on the direction the wind is blowing and its speed. This allows the fire perimeter to be estimated and then a team formation of UAVs to be defined for further monitoring [48, 63].

More complex fire models with more variables and data inputs have also been studied. These more advanced models often attempt to estimate the rate of fire spread based on wind speed and direction, terrain slopes, vegetation density, weather, and other variables. These models are often tested in a simulation [60, 78-80].

Other techniques propose a different model approach and characterize the fire, for example, they use multiple images to extract geometric features of the fire such as base perimeter, height, and slope. The extraction is performed using computer vision techniques (e.g. image segmentation), this is achieved by using multiple multimodal stereo vision systems from visible (NIR) *near-infrared images* to extract the fire area. Each stereo system provides an approximate 3D model of the fire; the models captured using multiple views are recorded to obtain the 3D model of the fire. This 3D model is tracked over time to calculate different fire characteristics such as height, width, slope, perimeter, area, volume, rate of spread, and their evolution over time [64].

4.6 Drone coordination strategy

The coordination strategy is an important component when deploying autonomous UAVs. The coordination strategy establishes the communication procedure, task assignment, and planning procedures. From the communication links established during the mission, three main schemes can be distinguished. First, for a single UAV, there is no coordination strategy since the UAV does not need to communicate with other UAVs. For multiple UAVs, route planning and task assignment are often solved by an optimization process or assumed to be so. One approach is to centralize the decision-making and route planning process in the emergency management center and only allow the UAV to communicate with it, but not with each other. Another approach is to address the problem of coordinating multiple entities in a distributed and decentralized manner. Each vehicle can connect to other UAVs, allowing distributed decision-making and communication with the emergency management center only for reporting observations, not for planning [46, 60, 61].

Incorporating more UAVs into the mission increases the area covered by the systems. In a so-called centralized strategy, all UAVs are coordinated by a single management or control center. This scheme can lead to more accurate forest fire georeferencing by allowing global situational awareness at all times. Another advantage of centralized communications is that it facilitates centralized processing and thus allows the use of smaller and more affordable UAVs, as they do not require high processing power. The main drawback of this approach is the need for a functional communication network that can connect to all UAVs at all times, which is not always possible when fire areas are remote [48, 77, 81].

On the other hand, in a decentralized communication scheme, UAVs communicate with each other to collaborate on route planning and optimal area coverage. Interaction with the emergency management or control center is kept to a minimum and typically only occurs at the beginning of a flight to receive initial flight coordinates or at the end of a flight for observation reporting and data transfers. The system is capable of performing more tasks autonomously and even covering larger areas using some UAVs as communication relays. The main advantages of this approach are reliability, as a link to the

management/control center does not need to be active at all times, and the possibility of operations in remote areas where global communication links are impractical. However, the added complexity imposes new challenges, as distributed coordination algorithms need to be developed and implemented [82] [20]. For the task of fire monitoring, some techniques propose a collaborative system in which unmanned aerial vehicles are sent to monitor fire and optimally cover the fire area [79].

This formation is achieved by detecting neighboring UAVs and reducing camera view overlaps while considering the location of the fire front. UAVs are also allowed to increase or decrease their altitude to control the resolution of captured images and provide optimal observation capabilities. This behavior is achieved with the application of a force field-based algorithm that simulates a UAV's attraction to the fire front and its repulsion from other UAVs. The attraction and repulsion forces are adapted by considering the confidence of the fire front and the estimated field of view of each UAV.

Decentralized approaches have also been used for direct firefighting using fire extinguishers, in this technique a coordination protocol is proposed in which the planned route of each UAV is optimized to minimize the distance to the detected fire perimeter; as a second phase, the trajectory of the unmanned aerial vehicles carrying fire extinguishing media is optimized by minimizing the distance to the fire center, this allows the solution to monitor a fire situation and provide optimal fire extinguisher delivery [78].

4.7 Using Cooperative Autonomous Systems

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) can play an important role in detecting and monitoring large forest fires. Multiple UAVs can collaborate in extracting important data and improving firefighting strategies. In addition, aerial vehicles can cooperate with unmanned ground vehicles (UGVs) in operational firefighting scenarios.

One type of cooperation may involve the use of UGVs to transport small, short-duration UAVs to detected fire zones and use them as refueling stations. For example, UAVs are transported by UGVs to a desired location and deployed to scout pre-assigned areas, if a UAV detects a fire, an alert is sent to the lead UGV and the rest of the fleet.

The lead calculates new optimal trajectories for the UAVs to control the fire perimeter [63]. In this scenario, it is assumed that both UAVs and UGVs have water-delivery and fire-fighting capabilities. UAVs are deployed in an optimal flight formation over the fire front area. UGVs are sent to prevent the spread of the fire and limit its spread using water and fire retardants.

Other techniques propose a cooperative multimodal UAV-UGV framework for large-scale wildfire detection and segmentation, 3D modeling, and strategic firefighting. The framework is composed of multiple UAVs and UGVs operating in a team-based cooperative mode. The vehicles are equipped with a multimodal stereo vision system like those developed for ground-based fire detection and 3D modeling [83]. The stereo system includes multispectral cameras operating in the visible and NIR spectrum for efficient fire detection and segmentation.

Each stereo system provides an approximate 3D model of the fire. The models captured using multiple views are recorded using inertial measurements, geospatial data, and the features extracted using computer vision to build the 3D model of the spreading fire front [84, 85]. Based on the 3D model of the fire, UAVs and UGVs can be strategically placed to capture complementary views of the firefront. This 3D model is tracked over time to calculate different three-dimensional characteristics of the fire such as height, width, slope, perimeter, area, volume, spread rate, and their evolution over time.

The extracted three-dimensional fire characteristics can be fed into a mathematical fire spread model to predict fire behavior and its spread over time. The data obtained allows for alerting and reporting on risk levels in the surrounding areas. The predicted fire spread can be mapped and used in an operational firefighting strategy [86]. Furthermore, this information can be used for the optimal deployment of UAVs and UGVs in the field. These types of structures can be combined with other firefighting resources such as firefighters, aerial firefighting aircraft, and future firefighting drones.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Unmanned aerial vehicles can be used in wildfire management systems to detect fires more quickly, provide images from hard-to-reach locations, make operations safer, and save lives. However, research and real-life experiences show that drone technologies in wildfire management systems need to be more efficient, which is evident in large-scale wildfires.

This chapter presents and analyses the different drone technologies for assistance in forest fire management. The capabilities of technologies incorporated into drones such as fire detection instruments, fire perception algorithms, and different coordination strategies in the mitigation management of a forest fire have been described. Unmanned aerial vehicles can play an important role in fighting forest fires, especially when they cover or affect large areas. Also, at present, there are still some limitations in the performance of UAVs, such as autonomy, reliability, and fault tolerance. Safety is also a concern, as there are risks associated with having UAVs flying over firefighters or near aircraft carrying water and fire retardants.

On another note, the importance of appropriate architecture, sensors, platforms, and remote sensing capabilities for UAV wildfire management was highlighted. Infrared cameras mounted on UAVs are often part of a multi-sensor payload, typically in combination with RGB and thermal sensors. This is convenient as operators can capture visual and thermal data simultaneously. It is more effective to aggregate knowledge from different sources than from a single sensor.

Despite the harsh weather conditions in a wildfire situation, UAVs must be capable of fighting fires as they increase in size, frequency, and intensity. UAVs must be highly energy efficient when dealing with large fires or operations lasting for a long time. Furthermore, when working with firefighters, UAVs must be reliable and equipped with advanced thermal sensors, longer flight times, heat resistance, obstacle avoidance capabilities, and waterproofing to operate in all temperatures and conditions. Therefore, there is a great urgency for further development in the aforementioned areas using robust and comprehensive optimization algorithms for wildfire management.

On the other hand, depending on the technological capabilities of the UAV, device vibration, poor camera quality, fast movement, and rotation of the UAV often disturb the images and result in poor-quality images. UAVs with machine learning and deep learning technology can address numerous operational and management challenges in forest fire management. In some cases, the sensors equipped on UAVs are inadequate to detect the information of a large-scale affected region.

Finally, wildfire management using UAVs still presents several drawbacks, such as high initial costs, loss of UAVs due to uncertainty or hardware failures, sensor capacity, technical issues, lack of established procedures to process massive amounts of data, and the need for specialists. Ultimately, robust wildfire management based on drone technology can yield significant social, economic, and environmental benefits associated with wildfire management, as well as improved decision-making.

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